

The effect of nursery rhymes to toddlers ages 3 to 7 years old undergoing chest imaging examination in selected hospitals

Sophia Sorelle H. Solomon*, Gaile Ann H. Marasigan, Jessica M. Solomon, Jonathan A. Kupahu
Radiologic Technology Department, School of Health Science Professions, St. Dominic College of Asia,
Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author

Abstract

Nursery rhymes are types of music that most children listen to that have become the most common therapy in providing healthcare. The study investigates how nursery rhymes affect the temperament level of pediatric patients, particularly the toddlers aged 3-7 years old undergoing chest imaging examination in selected hospitals in Metro Manila. Forty (40) respondents were randomly selected and divided into two groups: the control group and the experimental group. The control group are those who underwent chest imaging examination without the use of nursery rhymes, while the experimental group are those who underwent chest imaging examination with the use of nursery rhymes. Using a survey and observation, most of the respondents are females. Patients in the control group cited "intensity of emotional response" as the highest mean score of 3.3 with a "feisty" mood in temperament level, and the lowest indicators are "distractibility" and "attention span or persistence," which both obtained the lowest mean score of 2.5 with a "feisty" mood. The overall mean score for this group is 2.81 with a verbal interpretation of "feisty," while in the experimental group, "intensity of emotional response" obtained the highest mean score of 3.9, or "flexible" temperament level, and the lowest indicator is "quality of mood," which obtained the lowest mean score of 1.8 with the equivalent description of "fearful." The overall mean score for this group is 2.41 with a verbal interpretation of "feisty." There is a significant difference in the temperamental level of both control and experimental groups.

Keywords: Chest imaging examination; Therapy; Nursery rhymes; Temperament; Toddler.

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Introduction

In the United Kingdom and many other nations, nursery rhymes are traditional children's poems or songs that date back to the late eighteenth or early nineteenth centuries. They continue to engage in their poems and songs, spanning both adult and child generations. One of these that has been a part of their childhood for centuries are nursery rhymes. These rhymes are regarded by educators as timeless literature for teaching language and music (Cardany, 2013). Nursery rhymes are also a type of music that most children listen to, which has become the most common therapy in providing healthcare.

Mood and music are frequently related. One can feel joyful, depressed, energized, or calm after listening to a song. It is no surprise that music therapy has been explored for use in treating different medical illnesses because music can have a profound effect on a person's mindset and general well-being (Ulbricht, 2013). Although listening to music might be a useful way to improve your mood, it is becoming more obvious that music has many other advantages. As children grow, their development is also enhanced, and over time their hearing develops, allowing them to understand more of the tones and lyrics of a song.

Toddlers' rates of development vary. What is deemed "normal" varies greatly, and the child may be somewhat behind in some areas and ahead in others. A parent could speak with the child's healthcare professional about his or her potential delays (Coyne et al., 2014). As soon as the child grows, it undergoes a series of medical examinations and procedures.

One of the child's medical examinations in the radiology field is chest radiography. When a child or toddler exhibits fever, tachypnea, nasal flaring, retractions, grunting, rales, reduced breath sounds, and respiratory distress, chest radiography is recommended as the primary imaging examination to verify the diagnosis of pneumonia (O'Grady et al., 2014).

Tantrums are often driven by anxiety, and when a child is exposed to an environment that makes them anxious, the child would express it by throwing tantrums. A tantrum is a behavior that is motivated by fear and anxiety (Ogundele, 2018). Since fear indicates that a child is beginning to comprehend the world and how it functions, it is a perfectly natural aspect of growing up. They try to interpret its meaning for themselves (Young, 2016). According to Brooker et al. (2013), around six months of age, fearfulness in the presence of a stranger is thought to emerge, and throughout the first year of life, it increases.

A chest x-ray or chest radiography is performed in a standing, sitting, or lying position. When the child is being examined, the child will not feel any pain. An immobilization device is used when the child is uncooperative, such as the Pigg-o-stat, which is adjustable for the child's age, from infant to 3 and a half years of age (Noonan et al., 2017). Toddlers who are 3 to 7 years old can understand instructions and explanations when they are offered with an understanding of the child's likely perception (Long et al., 2019). Bjorkman (2014) states that the most frequent reason a child is sent for a radiographic evaluation is a suspected fracture. Nearly half (39%) of girls and two-thirds (64%) of boys are predicted to sustain an injury that requires a radiographic evaluation before the age of 15. Chest examination is by far the most frequently used diagnostic X-ray imaging procedure, with a percentage of 60% on children (Iacob et al., 2002).

The researchers have chosen this study so that they would know the effects of nursery songs on children, specifically toddlers aged 3 to 7 years old, as they undergo a chest imaging examination. As future radiographers, this study would help the researcher understand pediatric patients better and how music affects them while they undergo a specific medical procedure. The purpose of this study is to find out the effect of nursery songs on toddlers who undergo chest imaging examinations, to identify how music affects the variables such as the duration of the examination and the temperament of the child, and to analyze why music affects these variables when a toddler undergoes a chest imaging examination.

Statement of the Problem

The study determines the effect of children's songs on toddlers undergoing chest imaging examinations in two selected hospitals. The following questions were answered specifically.

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents?
 - 1.1. Classification of toddlers (going to school/not yet going to school)
 - 1.2. Sex
2. What is the temperamental level of the toddler after the chest imaging examination?
 - 2.1. Control group
 - 2.2. Experimental group
3. How long did the duration of the chest imaging examination last?
 - 3.1. Control group
 - 3.2. Experimental group
4. Is there a significant difference in the temperamental level and duration of time of the control and experimental group?

5. Is there a significant difference on the effect of nursery rhymes to toddlers undergoing chest imaging examination when grouped according to their demographic variables?

Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the temperamental level of the control and experimental group.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the duration of time of the control and experimental group.

Ho3: There is no significant difference on the effect of children's songs to toddlers undergoing chest imaging examination when grouped according to their elemental variables.

Review of Related Literature

Nursery Rhymes as a Song

Baleghizadeh and Dargahi (2010) found that children, especially those learning English as a second language, benefited most from the use of nursery rhymes. The conventional, straightforward, oral method is one way to teach sounds. Teaching children learning English as a second language the alphabet's sounds has long had a significant position in language pedagogy and greatly enhances their reading, speaking, and pronouncing abilities. The alternative is to provide them with multiple chances to experience the joy of simple nursery rhymes while also teaching them the language's sounds.

Nursery rhymes are a wide range of poems or rhymes for children, and these became songs with associated melodies. Among the features of folk music are nursery rhymes, which have been around for hundreds of years and are transmitted orally from one generation to the next. Nursery rhymes have many variations because, like folk songs, they have changed over time as diverse word and melody adaptations have been brought about by verbal communication, such as versions from the British Isles, particularly Scotland (Maiti & Naskar, 2017).

Throughout history, lullabies and nursery rhymes have mostly been employed as a teaching tool to educate children on historical events. The word "lullaby" became popular throughout time, which associates it with a calming song to comfort young children. But history demonstrates that certain lullabies are terrifying and everything but calming (Turpin & Green, 2018)

Music as Therapy

Even toddlers with challenges benefit from music therapy as they grow and develop. Private therapists, schools, clinics, and hospitals all provide music therapy to toddlers. The American Music Therapy Association (2005) defines music therapy as a recognized medical field that effectively meets the physical, emotional, cognitive, and social requirements of toddlers. After monitoring a toddler's behavior and social interactions, a music therapist can design an activity program for the child's unique needs. One of music therapy's advantages is stress reduction; it helps young patients manage their fear and anxiety during medical procedures. Additionally, it fosters socializing, self-expression, and word learning in the toddlers (Haering, 2020). Research supports the effectiveness of music therapy in various areas, including overall physical rehabilitation, movement facilitation, boosting motivation to participate in treatment, offering clients and their families emotional support, and giving them a way to express their emotions.

Certified music therapists are typically skilled musicians with extensive understanding of how music may stimulate emotional reactions to calm, uplift, or heal individuals (Franco et al., 2018). They use

this information along with their expertise with a broad range of musical genres to identify the one that will help you meditate or get through a difficult physical therapy session. Patients benefit greatly from music therapy, which helps lessen the negative effects of cancer treatment. This is because music helps people feel less anxious through radiation and chemotherapy. Additionally, music therapy aids in rehabilitation and physical therapy. Patients who use a playlist for their workouts are likely to find that the music helps them stay on track. Numerous studies indicate that during physical rehabilitation programs, music therapy improves people's emotional, cognitive, psychological, and physical functioning. This may also aid in the alleviation of pain. A wide range of patients, from those with severe acute pain to those with chronic pain, have been examined using music therapy. Music therapy helps people feel more in control of their suffering, lessens their perception of pain, lowers the amount of pain medication required, and helps them overcome depression.

According to Kemper and Danhauer (2005), music is frequently utilized to improve well-being, lower stress levels, and divert patients' attention from uncomfortable symptoms. Music seems to have direct physiological impacts through the autonomic nervous system, even though individual preferences vary greatly. For medical and surgical patients, patients in critical care units, patients undergoing procedures, adults, and children in particular, music significantly lowers anxiety and elevates mood.

Furthermore, music therapy has been utilized largely as an intervention to influence emotional states, in pain treatment, cognitive processing, and stress management (Avers et al., 2007). Increasing production of the stress hormone cortisol, which is known to inhibit immunological responses, is associated with stress. Music therapy has a beneficial impact on immunological responses or stress reduction. To improve the immune response and reduce stress in such circumstances, it should be viewed as a beneficial alternative to conventional pharmacologic therapy techniques.

Temperamental Traits and Types

According to Chess and Thomas (1996), psychologists have studied individual differences in people and have identified the following nine temperament levels. Children are often depicted or described in three adjectives. First is the "easy" or "flexible" child; these are about 40% of most groups of children. Children who are described as "flexible" are children with easy temperaments. They have regular biological rhythms, are flexible, friendly, and often in a mild to moderately upbeat mood. Such children are simple for caretakers to manage since they pick things up quickly, accept most new people and settings well, and tend to be happy and lightly communicate their dissatisfaction or unhappiness. The second is the "difficult" or "feisty" child; these are about 10% of the children in the group. The opposite of a flexible child is a feisty one, who normally adjusts slowly and fusses or even yells aloud at everything new. Too frequently, this kind of young person displays an unpleasant attitude and, if irritated, may even throw a fit. The third and last adjective that the children often describe is the "slow to warm up" or "fearful" child. This type of child is often also called the "shy" type and is about 15% of the children in the group. Children adjust very slowly and feel uneasy in unfamiliar situations or environments. In contrast to a feisty child, a terrified child tends to express their negative emotions gradually. The child's shyness instantly gets worse if they are forced or coerced into joining the group.

A child's activity level, biological regularity, adaptability, approach/withdrawal, sensitivity threshold, intensity of emotional response, distractibility, mood quality, and persistence/attention span are the nine temperamental features. The degree to which an individual reacts to both positive and negative circumstances is known as their intensity of emotional response. It is the degree to which a mood, whether positive or negative, is expressed energetically. Some people have extremely modest reactions to both positive and bad situations, while others have stronger reactions, which are known as "high intensity." High-intensity children react to things very strongly. Even if the issue is not serious, they will react strongly when something bad happens. Children who exhibit intense reactions may come off as exaggerating the situation. Children with lesser intensity will respond to both positive and negative events very minimally;

they might only smile when they hear good news. When anything happens to them, their reaction will be restricted, or they will not seem to respond at all. Recognizing the emotions of a child with low intensity can be challenging (Rymanowicz, 2017).

Attention span or persistence is the amount of time a person can persevere through a challenging task. It describes how long a person or child can and will continue to do a task, even if it is difficult. Youngsters with strong perseverance will put in a lot of effort to complete tasks they have begun and are likely to develop the skills they have mastered (e.g., riding a bike). When a child finds something challenging, they are more inclined to go on to something else. If they encounter a difficult task, they frequently feel overburdened and may become extremely irate or want assistance from an adult (Rymanowicz, 2017).

In quality of mood, positive moods are characterized by a lot of pleasant and joyful actions, while negative moods are characterized by fussy, depressing, and unpleasant behavior. Children who are more naturally upbeat are probably going to look joyful and lively most of the time. They will be able to get over unhappy times more easily. In discussions, they are frequently cheerful and upbeat and tend to be more positive. Children that are more naturally depressed could come out as more restrained rather than joyful. They might come out as depressed, gloomy, or pessimistic (Rymanowicz, 2017).

Theoretical Framework

The conceptual framework that was used is the Child's Hierarchy of Needs which is based on Maslow's theory. Maslow's hierarchy of needs is a psychological theory of motivation that consists of a five-tier model of human needs that can often be seen as a pyramid (McLeod, 2020). An individual must satisfy the lower level of hierarchy before progressing onto the higher level, but Maslow (1987) later clarified that satisfaction of needs is not an "all-or-none" phenomenon; instead, an individual could progress into a higher level even if it does not satisfy the lower level.

Maslow labeled the bottom four stages of the pyramid "deficiency needs" because, according to Burton (2012), a person experiences anxiety if their needs are not met but feels nothing if they are. These include safety needs, social needs like companionship and sexual intimacy, physiological requirements like eating, drinking, and resting, and ego needs like recognition and self-worth. Because it allows one to "self-actualize," or realize one's full potential as a human being, he went on to refer to the fifth level of the pyramid as a "growth need."

Maslow's hierarchy serves as the foundation for child development, and each of these stages will assist parents in understanding how to effectively care for young children and their unique requirements. Children are entirely reliant on others to meet their requirements since they frequently exhibit signals of insecurity and a need for safety, which probably puts a lot of strain and places the duty of understanding and appropriately meeting such requirements on parents (PhD in Parenting, 2010). Activity level, distractibility, approach or withdrawal, adaptability, attention span and persistence, intensity of reaction, threshold of responsiveness, and quality of mood are among the nine aspects or attributes that Chess and Thomas (1996) claim help identify temperament. By examining these dimensions, parents can not only discover the temperaments of their children but also learn how to interact and manage specific aspects of those temperaments to create an atmosphere of nurturing for the child and even avert many issues before they occur.

In this research paradigm (Figure 1), the researchers identified variables in determining the effect of children's songs on toddlers while undergoing a chest imaging examination. The independent variable in this study is the music for the experimental group, such as the nursery rhymes, used during the chest imaging examination, while on the controlled group there was no music used. The dependent variable in this study is the gender of the toddler and their classification of schooling, whether the toddler is already goes to school or not yet.

Figure 1. Research paradigm

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers used a quasi-experimental research design. The participants are not randomized to circumstances or sequences of conditions at random, despite the manipulation of the independent variable (Maciejewski, 2020). Quasi-experimental research avoids directionality concern by manipulating the independent variable prior to measuring the dependent variable. The researchers implemented the study by dividing the groups into two, a controlled group and an experimental group, who have undergone a basic chest imaging examination. However, the experimental group used a selection of nursery rhymes playing in the background. In these two groups, the researchers identified the effect of music on the pediatric patients' temperamental traits and on the duration of the examination.

Sampling and Population

Randomized sampling was used in this study. The participants of this study are the toddlers undergoing chest imaging examinations in the radiology department of selected hospitals in Metro Manila, specifically within the age bracket of 3-7 years old. The researchers obtained a population of 40 participants. To constantly focus and delimit the collection and analysis of data, potential participants were identified from the selected hospital in Metro Manila. Interchangeability of indices must also be met.

Research Protocol

The researchers conducted the research protocol in different steps: first, the researchers divided the sample population of the toddlers into two groups, which are the controlled group and the experimental group. Second, in line with the data privacy law, the identities of all 40 respondents were held in confidentiality limited to only the respondents and everyone part of the study. Third, the treatment was done. In the control group, a chest imaging examination is done with its basic protocols, while in the experimental group, the toddler has undergone the chest imaging examination with its basic procedure with nursery songs playing in the background; the music played as soon as the child entered the exposure room. The nursery rhymes that were played are *Twinkle, Twinkle Little Star*, *Mary Had a Little Lamb*, *Jack and Jill*, *Humpty Dumpty*, and *I'm a Little Teapot*. Fourth, the respondents in both control and experimental groups did the quasi-experimental study within one to four months, from eight to eleven in the morning, using only the exposure time as brief as 1-2 milliseconds (Cruz, 2016).

Research Instrument

The experiment used a temperament scale questionnaire with predetermined possible answers and a timer, which determined the factors that contributed to the effect of children's songs on toddlers undergoing chest imaging examination. The timer determined the difference between the duration of the chest imaging examination of the toddler in the two hospitals, since the first 20 participants of the two hospitals did not use nursery rhymes as a music therapy, while the other 20 participants of the two hospitals used nursery rhymes.

The other following different factors/elements that added to this study were the basis of formulating the temperamental scale questionnaire: a) profile of respondents with two (2) questions, b) the classification of the toddler with only one (1) question and c) the temperamental scale questionnaire consists of the eight temperamental traits: approach / withdrawal, which is the toddler's initial reaction to the new environment; activity level, which is the amount of physical motion of the toddler during the examination; intensity of emotional response; which is the amount of energy the toddler commonly used to express emotions; adaptability, which is how easily the toddler adjust to the changes in routine of the examination; distractibility, which is how easily a toddler's thought attention are interrupted by things going on around him; quality or mood which is the amount of pleasant, joyful and friendly behavior versus the unpleasant, frowning and unfriendly behavior of the toddler towards the examination; sensitivity threshold, which is how sensitive the toddler is in the selective channels: touch or pain and hearing or sound; and persistence / attention span, which is the length of time the toddler continues to listen and obey the task of the radiographer. The research temperamental scale was adapted from the other research studies.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at an x-ray department from two hospitals, specifically at Pasig City Children's Hospital and Ospital ng Parañaque. The hospitals that the researchers selected are both government hospitals. The researchers only selected two hospitals because the research is a quasi-experimental study and for the researchers' convenience because they were on duty as interns in the two hospitals.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers conducted the data gathering in different steps: first, approval was obtained from the Head Department Office to pursue the study; second was the selection of the hospitals; and third, a letter was given to the Head Department Office of the selected hospital to pursue the study. After the consent was given, the researchers then informed the radiologist by securing a letter for the purpose of the study and that the researchers will use a quasi-experimental study. Then, the researchers conducted a quasi-experiment using the temperamental scale and a timer for the measuring of time of the toddler's medical examination. Lastly, the acquired data was gathered and was statistically treated. The quasi-experiment was done in two selected hospitals in Metro Manila.

Statistical Treatment

Frequency and percentage were used to determine the profile of toddler respondents according to their classification of toddler and sex. Meanwhile, the mean score was used to analyze the temperament level of the respondents. The three adjectives that were used for the verbal interpretation of the mean scores are "flexible," "feisty," and "fearful," wherein:

Flexible—This ranges from the score of 3.68 to 5.0.

Feisty—This ranges from the score of 2.34 to 3.67.

Fearful—This ranges from the score of 1.0 to 2.33.

A one-way analysis of variance was used to determine whether there is a difference between the effect of children's songs on toddlers undergoing chest imaging examination for control and experimental groups. The t-test assesses whether the means of two groups are statistically different from each other.

Results and Discussion

Problem 1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents?

Table 1. Frequency Distribution and Percentage According to Classification of Toddler (n=40)

Classification of Toddler	Group	Frequency	Percentage
Attending School	Control	11	27.5%
	Experimental	17	42.5%
Not yet Attending School	Control	9	22.5%
	Experimental	3	7.5%

Based on Table 1, the classification of toddlers was divided into two groups: attending school and not yet attending school. Each classification has two groups: control and experimental. Toddlers attending school during the control group have a frequency of 11 or 27.5%, and for the experimental group, the total frequency was 17 with 42.5%. For the toddlers not yet attending the school, 9 or 22.5% was the disseminated frequency for the control group. For the experimental group, 3 is the computed frequency at a percentage of 7.5%. Most of the toddlers that undergo the examination are already attending school. The toddlers have no effect when they are undergoing chest imaging examination, whether they are going or not going to school, if they can understand the basic instructions for the examination.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution and Percentage According to Sex

Sex	Group	Frequency	Percentage
Male	Control	11	27.5%
	Experimental	6	15%
Female	Control	9	22.5%
	Experimental	14	35%

In Table 2, the gender of toddlers was disseminated, matching the control group and experimental group for both males and females. The male control group has a total frequency of 11, or 27.5%, while the male experimental group has a total frequency of 6 at a percentage of 15. For the female control group, 9 was the computed total frequency with 22.5%, and for the female experimental group, 14 was the computed frequency with 35%. Chest imaging examination for toddlers did not affect whether the male or female toddler, if the toddler can fully understand and follow the simple instruction of the radiographer, but some of the toddlers, regardless of gender, are very brave. It depends on how their parents raised them.

Problem 2. What is the temperamental level of the toddler after the chest imaging examination?

Gleaned from Table 3 are the results of the temperament level of the control group respondents. Among twenty (20) identified indicators, the intensity of emotional response obtained the highest mean score of 3.3 with an equivalent description of “feisty” in temperament level, and the lowest indicator is on both distractibility and attention span/persistence; they both obtained the lowest mean score of 2.5 with the same equivalent description of “feisty.” The overall mean score for this group is 2.81 with a verbal interpretation of “feisty.”

Table 3. Temperament Level of the Control Group after the Chest Imaging Examination

Temperament	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
Approach/Withdrawal	3.25	Feisty
Intensity of Emotional Response	3.3	Feisty
Distractibility	2.5	Feisty
Sensitivity Threshold	2.85	Feisty
Activity Level	2.8	Feisty
Adaptability	2.65	Feisty
Quality of Mood	2.65	Feisty
Attention Span / Persistence	2.5	Feisty
Total Mean Score	2.81	Feisty

Legend: Flexible = 3.68 – 5.0; Feisty = 2.34 – 3.67; Fearful = 1.0 – 2.33

Based on the table, the toddler who undergoes chest imaging examination with its basic protocols has the highest temperament level of intensity of emotional response, while the lowest temperament level is distractibility. In this result, the highest score means positive while the lowest scores mean negative. Since most of the children are unfamiliar with the environment inside the exposure room in the radiology department, they tend to have a low intensity of reaction because the radiographer tends to explain first to the child what they will be doing; most likely the radiographers would tell the child that they will only be having a picture and that they only need to smile. In some other cases when the child is dramatic, they need to be immobilized so that the examination can be done properly. The lowest temperament level is distractibility and attention span or persistence, with most of the children in the control group that undergo chest imaging examination with its basic protocols having high distractibility and low persistence. Toddlers tend to be easily distracted inside the exposure room, and when they are distracted, the toddler's persistence is low, which makes the radiographer use some restraints so that the procedure would be done properly.

Table 4. Temperament Level of the Experimental Group after the Chest Imaging Examination

Temperament	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
Approach/Withdrawal	3.65	Feisty
Intensity of Emotional Response	3.9	Flexible
Distractibility	2.25	Fearful
Sensitivity Threshold	1.9	Fearful
Activity Level	1.95	Fearful
Adaptability	1.85	Fearful
Quality of Mood	1.8	Fearful
Attention Span / Persistence	1.95	Fearful
Total Mean Score	2.41	Feisty

Legend: Flexible = 3.68 – 5.0; Feisty = 2.34 – 3.67; Fearful = 1.0 – 2.33

Gleaned from Table 4 are the results of the temperament level of the experimental group respondents; among twenty (20) identified indicators, intensity of emotional response obtained the highest mean score of 3.9 with an equivalent description of “flexible” in temperament level, and the lowest indicator is quality of mood, which obtained the lowest mean score of 1.8 with the equivalent description of “fearful.” The overall mean score for this group is 2.41 with a verbal interpretation of “feisty.”

Based on the table, the toddler who underwent a chest imaging examination with its basic protocols that had a nursery rhyme playing in its background has the highest temperament level of intensity of emotional response, while the lowest temperament level is the quality of mood. Since there was another factor added during the examination, most of the toddler's mood is negative. Most of the toddlers were fearful when there was added noise to their surroundings.

Problem 3. How long did the duration of the chest imaging examination last?

Table 5. Duration of the Chest Imaging Examination

Group	Average Time (in seconds)
Control	232.6
Experimental	257.4

In Table 5, the duration of chest imaging examination for the control group is 232.6 seconds, while in the experimental group it is 257.4 seconds. It shows that the control group has a short period of time for the chest examination. The child's age, level of cooperation with the radiographer, and the number of areas to be captured affect how long it takes. The process takes just a few seconds to obtain each photograph. The complete examination typically lasts less than five to fifteen minutes; however, sitting the child and getting ready for the x-ray may take some time (Cain, 2017).

The length of time in chest imaging examination for the toddlers depends on how they cooperated with the radiographer's instruction. The more they cooperate with the radiographer, the shorter the procedure will be, and there will be less exposure to the radiation. If the child is not cooperative, the examination will take too long to get good image quality and possibly require a repeat exposure.

Problem 4. Is there a significant difference in the temperamental level and duration of time of the control and experimental groups?

Table 6. Significant Difference on the Temperamental Level and Duration of Time on Control and Experimental Groups using One-Way ANOVA

Variables	F Value	df	P value (Sig.)	Interpretation	Analysis
Temperament	3.833	2	.050	Significant Difference	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Duration of Intervention	1.854	2	.181	No Significant Difference	Fail to Reject the Null Hypothesis

Table 6 shows the test of significant difference in the mean score on the temperamental level and duration of time on control and experimental groups. One-way ANOVA was calculated comparing the mean score of participants in terms of their behaviors and the duration of the intervention. The results revealed that there was a significant difference found in the temperament (F(2): 3.833, $p < .05$); particularly, the control group showed a more accepted behavior rather than their counterpart (control group mean score = 2.81; experimental group mean score = 2.41). In terms of the duration of the intervention, the results showed that there was also a significant difference found among the two groups (F(2): 1.854, $p < .05$).

Gleaned from Table 6 is the test for significant differences on the temperamental level and duration of time on control and experimental groups. In the temperament level, the computed significant value is .050, which has a significant difference; therefore, it is recommended to reject the null hypothesis. On the other hand, the computed significant value is .181, which has no significant difference; therefore, it has failed to reject the null hypothesis.

The temperament level of a toddler has a significant difference from the control and experimental groups because, based on the observation, the toddler shows different temperamental traits during the imaging examination. Most likely, they show the temperament trait of distractibility and attention span or persistence. The exposure room is a new environment for the toddlers, and when they had their examination, most of them were done in a supine position. When the toddler gets distracted, their attention quickly shifts to another, and since their attention span becomes higher, the toddler feels overwhelmed and struggles in the situation they are in.

In the experimental group where there is a nursery rhyme playing in the background, the toddler tends to show the temperamental trait of quality of mood since they tend to hear too much noise. Other than the nursery rhyme playing, the radiographer also talks to the parent or guardian of the toddler who accompanies them during the examination. Therefore, the child’s mood starts to be negative. Based on the researchers’ observation, when there is a nursery rhyme added, the toddler appears to be more subdued than happy. They have an expression on their face that is calmer, yet they refused the examination, thus resulting in the use of restraints. The radiographer would tell the parents to lay the child down and hold their arms and legs. When the child is in this position, they throw a much more negative mood, which results in crying.

Problem 5. Is there a significant difference on the effect of nursery rhymes to toddlers undergoing chest imaging examination when grouped according to their demographic variables?

Table 7. Significant Difference on the Effect of Nursery Rhymes to Toddler Undergoing Chest Imaging Examination when Grouped According to their Demographic Variables using the Independent Sample T-Test

Variables	F Value	df	P value (Sig.)	Interpretation	Analysis
Sex	.677	38	.416	No Significant Difference	Fail to Reject the Null Hypothesis
Classification of Toddler	.299	38	.588	No Significant Difference	Fail to Reject the Null Hypothesis

Table 7 showed a significant difference in the effect of nursery rhymes on toddlers undergoing chest imaging examination when grouped according to their demographic variables. An independent samples t-test was calculated comparing the mean score of participants in terms of the temperament behaviors and their biographic variables. The results revealed that there was no significant difference found in the classification of toddlers and their sex when compared with their behavior during the radiographic examination ($t(38) : .677, p > .05$; $t(38) : .299, p > .05$).

There is no difference in the effect of nursery rhymes on toddler who was undergone chest imaging examination when it comes to their demographic profile; thus, it does not define the reaction of their behavior when they undergo to the examination. When it comes to the behavior of some toddlers, they will feel distracted because they do not know what is happening.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, most respondents are attending school. Children these days are eager to attend school even if they are as young as three years old. Children are also fast learners these days because of the technology that surrounds us, such as learning through the internet, television shows for kids, and mobile applications that enhance the child’s way of thinking.

Most patients are females having a chest imaging examination. Toddlers that underwent chest imaging examination in the controlled group have shown the temperamental trait of distractibility and attention span or persistence with a feisty mood. Toddlers tend to be easily distracted inside the exposure room, hence their low persistence. Most of the toddlers could not finish the chest imaging examination because they are afraid of certain factors, such as the use of x-ray tubes.

Toddlers that underwent chest imaging examination in the experimental group have shown the temperamental trait with a fearful mood. Nursery rhymes played during the chest imaging examination make the child more excited and tend to make them more hyperactive. Most toddlers showed negative

quality of mood because they tend to be afraid. Toddlers heard instead the voice of the radiographer ordering the parents to hold their child's arms and legs while undergoing the examination.

The duration of the chest imaging examination in the control group is much shorter than in the experimental group. The examination took long in the experimental group because of the nursery rhymes that were played during the examination. The ALARA principle is always prioritized in the exposure room to lessen the exposure of the child to radiation.

This shows that there is a significant difference in the temperamental level of control and experimental groups. Also, there is no significant difference in the duration of time on control and experimental groups. It shows that toddlers tend to be more distracted and have a negative quality of mood, which results in crying; thus, they get to be afraid since their arms and legs are being stretched. Some of the toddlers prior to the chest imaging examination were first being brought to the laboratory for tests. When the toddler is in the exposure room, they become more afraid even if there are nursery rhymes playing in the background; therefore, they feel that they will be hurt because of the experience in the laboratory. This implies that there is no significant difference in the effect of children's songs on toddlers undergoing chest imaging examinations when grouped according to their demographic variables.

Recommendations

The researchers recommend discussing the benefits of music with children attending school and how medical examinations, such as chest imaging, are done. They can be explained in an easier way so that the child can understand, such as saying that having a chest imaging is like only taking a picture. The researchers recommend using more than two hospitals as a reference. They shall continue to observe the toddlers who underwent chest imaging examination in different radiology departments and to observe the female versus male ratio of the toddlers.

Proper explanation of the procedures to the toddler and to his or her parents shall be given by the radiologic technologists when undergoing the chest imaging examination. The radiographer who performs the chest imaging examination on the toddler may play with the child by letting him or her touch the beam of the x-ray tube. He or she may explain to the parents to give support and reassurance to their child.

The researchers also recommend proper explanation of the procedures, specifically when it comes to immobilizing their child. The radiographer may tell the parents that they need to stretch the child's arms and legs so that it does not superimpose the area to be examined. The use of play therapy may be effective instead of music therapy because the researchers observed that the toddler responds well when they are being played. This may also be useful and can be tested during the examination.

Hospitals must at least add interior designs to their machines and surroundings. With this, it will divert their attention, which may help the toddlers feel comfortable and relaxed at the same time. Both parties may benefit from the participants involved, the radiographer and the patient themselves, having a more relaxing and easy way of doing the x-ray procedure. Toddlers may first have the chest imaging examination before the laboratory examination.

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